

THE PLACE OF AMIR TEMUR IN WORLD HISTORY

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Abstract: The article describes the political and military activities of Amir Temur in the military field, which left a deep mark on world martial arts.

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Amir Temur made successful campaigns against India, Khorasan, Iran, the Golden Horde, Mongolia and many other countries in order to achieve his great goal of building a great empire. During these large-scale marches, Sahibkiran uses a variety of fighting techniques that are perfect for each other. Due to the military tactics used by Amir Temur in the battles, many unruly fortresses were captured one after another with little losses in the army. Therefore, military history rightly recognizes Temurbek as one of the greatest commanders in the world[1].

The positive changes that took place in the social, political and economic life of Amir Temur as a result of his accession to the throne are reflected in the military and military artshows. His military prowess is evident in two main ways: as a skilled military organizer and as a renowned commander¹. As a great military leader and innovative military organizer, Amir Temur was able to create a highly disciplined army, to lead the troops in an artistic manner during the war, to send troops to the places where the fate of the war would be decided in a timely manner. will be able to overcome obstacles and ideas with entrepreneurship, to keep the fighting spirit in the army at the required level[2].

Amir Temur's army was well-organized and well-organized to conquer many countries. Determining and regulating the state of the army is called yasol. Improved by Sahibkiran from battle to battle, the army is armed with the most advanced weapons and equipment of its time, equipped with the same type of weapons, armor, parts of each other's heads, holding the flag or differentiated by birth[3].

The method of warfare used by Amir Temur in military conflicts differed from the fighting order of the armies of the great empires of his time, the Qarakhanids, Ghaznavids, Khorezmshahs, Seljuks, and Genghis Khans, which were divided into seven parts. Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi's "Zafarnoma" gives a detailed account of the seven-part structure of the Sahibkiran military method of warfare. In order to protect the wings of his army from the enemy's attack during the battle and,

conversely, to bypass the enemy forces from the side and strike him from behind, the cavalry unit-kunbul or kumbul, in some sources, the introduction of kanbul-was one of his great contributions to the development of martial arts. Only five centuries after this method of warfare, the army of Napoleon Bonaparte, the famous 19th century military leader, had a unit that defended the wings of the army in combat order[4].

Amir Temur paid special attention to the appointment of experienced and talented generals in military battles. In the process, it's mostly the martial arts themselves fully aware of the secrets of the enemy, well-versed in the instructions to disperse the enemy, courageous and quick in difficult situations, able to withstand any obstacles, to join the army Only those who were able to eliminate the unforeseen riots in a timely manner were appointed by Temurbek. The event, organized by Sahibkiran, ensures high efficiency in the use of military methods. In particular, Amir Temur showed great courage in capturing fortresses during his military campaigns in Khorasan, the Caucasus, Iran and India by talented generals[5].

Amir Temur was constantly thinking about the management of his army and troops, the improvement of new methods of military march. In particular, it is stated in "Temur's Statutes": At night, I would lie in bed, thinking about how to run the country, and imagining the means to do it. I would imagine the ways to conquer other countries, how to attack and how to retreat. I would think about how I would deal with my soldiers, how I would discipline them, what I would do to whom, and I would not make a mistake."5 We can also see from the above that Sahibkiran was never arrogant despite being such a great commander. Not only did he use new fighting techniques, but he also constantly thought about how to retreat and re-enter the battle in case of losing the battle[6].

Amir Temur pays great attention to small battles as well as big battles. On his orders, when the number of enemy troops on the battlefield was less than twelve thousand cavalry, the troops were commanded by Amir ul-Umar. There were also twelve from the provinces and districts in the battle a thousand horsemen accompanied him. Amir al-'Umara was accompanied by commanders, centurions and deputies, who informed Sahibkiran a day before the enemy's troops were to arrive. Despite the small size of this army, the tactical correctness of the army by the great commander was a key factor in ensuring victory in the battles. In particular, it is stated in "Temur's Statutes": let there be three fajj, one fajw in the courtyard, and one fajj in the guard. Let the baron himself consist of hirovul, chapovul and shikavul. In the same way, the cavalry should consist of hirovul,

chapovul and shikavul. "6 In addition to the formation of the army, Amir Temur also paid special attention to its location. Sahibkiran orders Amir ul-Umaro to consider four factors when choosing a battlefield. These are:

The first is its proximity to water. The second is the security of the place where the soldier is kept.

The third is to be above the place where the enemy army is standing and not to be exposed to the sun, so that the sun's rays do not dazzle the soldiers.

Fourth, the front of the battlefield should be open and spacious.

Again, Sahibkiran ordered that the day before the war, they should line up the army and, in accordance with the rules, divide it into fajjas and march towards the enemy. The heads of the horses should be directed in the desired direction and should not turn left or right on the road. He also said, "As soon as the eyes of the soldiers fell on the enemy's army, they shouted, 'Allahu akbar!' Let them say the takbir and attack the enemy with a trumpet. "

At that time, when almost all nations did not line up in order during the war, they fought in groups, without tactical considerations, gave in to their courage and threw themselves at the enemy in a chaotic manner. Amir Temur's troops lined up in orderly lines. will consist of several parts, and they will be introduced into the battle one by one, and finally the enemy with the final attacks weakened and exhausted, a strong and resilient reserve battle, consisting of the best fighters, which could always ensure victory, was introduced[7].

In conclusion, Sahibkiran was the first in the world to evaluate the opponent in a suitable way and introduced the methods of fighting in accordance with twelve thousand, forty thousand and more than forty thousand opponents. The great commander's great attention to relations with the generals in order to carry out the methods of warfare in a proper manner also ensured the victory of the army in the battles. Amir Temur's style of defending the main wings of the army was one of the great contributions to the development of world martial arts. Amir Temur was the great commander of his time and introduced new procedures and methods that had not been used in any army or military conflict before. Today, the fact that many countries around the world use Sahibkiran's military methods in the training of their armies testifies to the perfect structure of the discipline and tactics he introduced as a great commander, as well as a strong army.

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